

MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMIZATION OF MULTI-STAGE NEUROBLASTOMA CHEMOTHERAPY BASED ON A NONLINEAR COMPROMISE SCHEME AND THE HYBRID PADÉ-ADOMIAN-MSDTM METHOD

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Abstract

An algorithm for multi-criteria optimization of the multi-stage neuroblastoma chemotherapy process has been developed, based on Voronin's nonlinear compromise scheme and the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MSDTM. The terminal control problem for chemotherapeutic drug concentration is formulated as the minimization of a vector criterion that includes tumor burden, total toxicity, immune deficit, and control energy, subject to terminal conditions on residual tumor mass. The application of the differential transformation apparatus allows partial criteria to be expressed as analytical functions of the control free-parameter vector, reducing the multi-criteria problem to solving a system of nonlinear algebraic equations without numerical ODE integration. Numerical simulation results for various neuroblastoma morphotypes confirm the algorithm's ability to flexibly adapt the treatment strategy: a reduction in systemic toxicity of 6-62% and minimization of immune deficit by 47% are achieved while guaranteeing the target therapeutic outcome.

Keywords: neuroblastoma, multi-criteria optimization, nonlinear compromise scheme, differential transform method, Adomian polynomials, Padé approximation, terminal control.

1. Introduction

High-risk neuroblastoma remains one of the most critical problems in pediatric oncology: five-year survival under standard INRGSS/COG protocols does not exceed 40-50% [1]. Modern treatment, including induction chemotherapy, high-dose consolidation, and immunotherapy, is characterized by a narrow therapeutic window and high variability in drug response. Such clinical instability is due not only to genetic differences among patients but also to the tumor's ability to rapidly adapt during treatment. A fundamental barrier to personalization is biological heterogeneity and the phenotypic plasticity first systematically described therein - the ability of cells to reversibly transition from adrenergic (x_A) to mesenchymal (x_M) status [2]. This mechanism allows the tumor to form dynamic resistance: in response to therapeutic stress, cells switch to a quiescent state, becoming insensitive to cytostatics and serving as sources of subsequent relapses. This phenomenon is often ignored by unified protocols that do not account for the individual dynamic phenotype-switching profile.

The problem of optimal control in cancer chemotherapy has a long developmental history. The pioneering work of Murray [3] laid the mathematical foundation for applying variational calculus and Pontryagin's maximum principle to minimize tumor volume subject to toxicity constraints. Fundamental contributions to understanding the structure of optimal control were made by Ledzewicz and Schättler [4], who showed that in models with immune response, the control strategy has a complex singular structure. Further studies [5-7] demonstrated the high sensitivity of such solutions to the choice of criterion and the accuracy of initial diagnostics. Despite theoretical rigor, classical analytical approaches remain limited by the complexity of solving two-point boundary value problems and their low robustness to inevitable parameter perturbations.

With the development of computational power, the emphasis has shifted to numerical methods. Direct collocation and model predictive control (MPC) allow for the handling of strict constraints; however, their high iterative complexity impedes implementation in wearable medical devices [8]. Deep reinforcement learning methods demonstrate adaptability but are perceived by the medical community as "black boxes" [8]. Moreover, most clinical decision support systems (CDSS) apply linear criterion aggregation with fixed weights, requiring subjective manual tuning. In this context, Voronin's nonlinear compromise scheme [9] is promising: it possesses the unique property of automatically amplifying the weight of whichever criterion is currently closest to its critical boundary (e.g., the toxicity limit), ensuring therapeutic safety without the need for expert re-tuning of weights.

However, the effectiveness of any control strategy critically depends on the accuracy of identifying the object's parameters. In the context of oncology, this means that the mathematical model must reflect the individual aggressiveness of a specific patient's tumor based on objective diagnostic data. A significant gap in the literature remains the absence of a direct, reproducible link between formalized clinical morphometry and the parameters of dynamic models. Most authors use abstract coefficients, which deprives models of personalization power. The solution lies in translational medicine: using histological standards to calibrate ODE systems. The Shimada histological classification [10], based on the nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio (R_{NC}), mitotic index (MKI), and lymphocyte infiltration (TIL), is the recognized INRG standard [1]. Work [11] laid the foundations for parametrizing ODE models via these features; the present work advances this approach toward intelligent control synthesis.

The aim of this work is to develop a method for intelligent control synthesis of multi-stage chemotherapy that transforms static Shimada factors into dynamic therapy parameters based on Voronin's scheme and the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method.

2. Mathematical Model of Tumor Dynamics

The tumor dynamics are described by a system of generalized ODEs accounting for the phenotypic plasticity of the tumor - transitions between adrenergic (x_A) and mesenchymal (x_M) states of tumor cells [2]:

$$\dot{x}_A = \alpha_A x_A \left(1 - \frac{x}{K}\right) - \beta_A x_A z - \gamma_A c x_A + \varphi_M x_M - \varphi_A x_A, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{x}_M = \alpha_M x_M \left(1 - \frac{x}{K}\right) - \beta_M x_M z - \gamma_M c x_M + \varphi_A x_A - \varphi_M x_M, \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{p} = \sigma - \mu p - \delta_p x p + \rho_p p z, \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{z} = \lambda x z - \nu z + \xi x, \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{c} = -k_e c + u(t), \quad (5)$$

where $x = x_A + x_M$ is the total tumor population density, and ξx describes the antigenic stimulation of the immune response by tumor burden.

This five-component system extends the classical tumor-immune interaction framework [7], incorporating immune-mediated cytotoxicity [4] and stromal remodeling [5].

The full five-component nonlinear formulation used in this study was originally introduced in our earlier work [11]:

In equations (1)-(5), the following notation is adopted: $x_A(t)$, $x_M(t)$ - densities of cells of corresponding phenotypes; $p(t)$ - density of the stromal (neuropilar) component of the tumor microenvironment; $z(t)$ - density of immune effector cells (intensity of the immune response); $c(t)$ - drug concentration; $u(t)$ - infusion intensity of the chemotherapeutic agent (control input).

In equation (3), the positive term $\rho_p p z$ reflects immune-mediated remodeling of the tumor microenvironment, leading to an increase in neuropilar stromal density. The term $\lambda x z$ in equation (4) describes the proliferation of already-activated immune cells under antigenic tumor stimulation, while the term ξx models the primary recruitment of immune cells from the peripheral immune system in response to tumor burden growth.

The present study employs an extended tumor–microenvironment–immunity model that accounts for phenotypic plasticity (adrenergic and mesenchymal states) [2], immune-mediated stromal remodelling [5], and antigen-driven immune activation [4]. This model represents a biologically richer refinement of the baseline tumor–stroma–immunity system used in earlier works on terminal optimal control. The extended formulation is essential in the multi-criteria setting, where conflicting therapeutic objectives naturally arise and require a more detailed representation of tumor heterogeneity and immune–stromal interactions.

2.1. Parameterization of the Control Object

To implement personalized optimization, the coefficients of system (1)-(5) are adapted to the patient's biological profile through a functional relationship with the Shimada classification factors [1,10] (Table 1). This allows static histology data to be transformed into the optimization parameter space, providing an individual balance between efficacy and toxicity in the compromise scheme.

Table 1 - Grouping of model parameters for optimization tasks

Parameter Group	Functional Dependence	Effect on Optimization Criteria
Proliferation and Carrying Capacity (α, K)	$\alpha = \alpha_0(1 + \alpha_1 R_{NC} + \alpha_2 A_{\text{atypia}})$, $K = K_0(1 + b_1 \rho + b_2 \eta)$	Determine the potential tumor growth rate and the maximum tolerable population volume.
Immune Status (β, μ, σ)	$\beta = f(\lambda_{TIL})$, $\mu, \sigma = f(MKI)$	Characterize the intensity of the natural anti-tumor response and the stromal degradation rate.
Stress and Therapy Response ($\lambda, \delta, \gamma, \varphi$)	$\theta_j = \theta_{j,0}(1 + g_j S)$, where $\theta \in \{\lambda, \delta, \gamma, \varphi\}$	Determine drug sensitivity, resource depletion rate, and phenotypic plasticity risk.

In the formulas of Table 1, the following morphometric features are used: R_{NC} - nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio; A_{atypia} - degree of nuclear atypia; ρ - local cell density; η - degree of neuropil (stroma) maturity; λ_{TIL} - intensity of tumor lymphocyte infiltration; MKI - mitotic-karyorrhectic index (indicator of proliferative activity) [1,10].

The parameters $\lambda, \delta, \gamma, \varphi$ are critical for control synthesis, as they describe the dynamic response of the system to external action: γ - tumor sensitivity to cytostatics; φ - phenotypic plasticity coefficient (intensity of cell transition to a resistant state); λ, δ - indicators of immunity depletion and tissue degradation under the influence of systemic stress factor S .

Increasing S corresponds to higher treatment-induced stress, which reduces drug sensitivity (γ) and accelerates immune depletion (λ, δ). S is a dimensionless systemic stress factor, estimated from the patient's clinical status (e.g., performance status, cumulative organ toxicity score). For numerical experiments in this work, S is set to 0.5 for the aggressive morphotype and 0.2 for the favorable morphotype.

The proposed parameterization follows the parametrization framework introduced in [12], and allows static histology data to be transformed into the optimization parameter space. This analytical approach solves tasks that are critical for multi-criteria synthesis:

- **Weight Individualization:** The optimization algorithm accounts for individual sensitivity γ and the risk of immunity suppression, directly affecting the position of the Voronin compromise point.
- **Dimensionality Reduction:** Disease heterogeneity is reflected through equation coefficients without increasing the number of phase variables, which is critically important for the speed of the MsDTM method.
- **Clinical Interpretability:** Optimization results (optimal doses and intervals) become derivatives of verifiable risk markers (MKI, TIL), which simplifies the integration of the algorithm into medical practice.

To avoid dimensional inconsistency, all variables x_A, x_M, p, z, c are normalized by K , and are therefore dimensionless. The sensitivity parameter γ is reduced to a dimensionless form by scaling: $\tilde{\gamma} = \gamma \cdot K$.

2.2. Problem Statement for Control Algorithm Synthesis

The neuroblastoma therapy process is multi-stage and is characterized by changes in dosing regimes and cytotoxic action mechanisms. To formalize the problem, the entire treatment period $[t_0, T]$ is divided into p time sub-intervals (stages) of duration T_i [3-6,8]:

$$T_i = t_i - t_{i-1}, i = \overline{1, p}, \sum_{i=1}^p T_i = T,$$

where T is the total therapy duration. It is assumed that within each sub-interval the structural parameters of the system remain unchanged, and the control $u(t)$ is a continuous function. All changes in the form of prescribed jumps occur only at the boundaries of the time intervals of each therapy stage.

Then, optimization of the control process can be applied independently to each of the p intervals, and the resulting system trajectory is reconstructed piecewise with matching of the boundary conditions at the stage junctions [13]

For control synthesis, the mathematical model of the neuroblastoma therapy process at each i -th stage is represented as a vector differential state equation:

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = f_i(t, x_i, u_i, v_i), \quad x_i(t_{i-1}) = x_i^0, \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \quad (6)$$

where $x_i = x_i(t)$ is the n -dimensional state vector of the biosystem (including the densities of tumor cell populations x_A, x_M , immune effectors z , stroma p , and current drug concentration c); u_i is the m -dimensional control vector (infusion intensity of the chemotherapeutic agent); v_i is the ℓ -dimensional perturbation vector (parameter uncertainty, individual patient response variability, mutational shifts); f_i is a continuous and continuously differentiable vector function describing the biological growth rates, cell death, and pharmacokinetics; $t \in (t_i - t_{i-1})$ is the time interval of the i -th therapy stage.

Thus, the state vector has dimension $n = 5$: $x_i = (x_A, x_M, p, z, c)^T$, the control vector dimension $m = 1$: $u_i = u(t)$, and the perturbation vector v_i is ℓ -dimensional in accordance with the number of uncertain biosystem parameters.

The coupling of the terminal and initial conditions of the process control segments is specified in the form of boundary conditions:

$$\varphi_i[x_i(T_i), x_{i+1}^0; u_i(T_i), u_{i+1}^0; T_i] = 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, p. \quad (7)$$

The terminal control problem consists in transferring system (6) from the initial state $x_i(t_0)$ to the final state $x_r(T)$, which is defined at time $t = T$ by the q -dimensional ($q \leq n$) tumor reduction vector equation:

$$S[x_p(T), T] = 0. \quad (8)$$

The quality of the process is evaluated by a set of partial criteria I_j defined by functionals:

$$I_j = G_j[x_p(T), T] + \sum_{i=1}^p \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} \Phi_{ij}(t, x_i(t), u_i(t), v_i(t)) dt, \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, p, \quad (9)$$

where the prescribed functions G_j and Φ_{ij} have continuous partial derivatives with respect to x_i, u_i, v_i and describe the biological and economic costs of therapy; p is the number of therapy stages, r is the number of partial optimality criteria.

The partial criteria (9) are components of the r -dimensional vector criterion $I(u) = (I_1(u), I_2(u), \dots, I_r(u))$, bounded by the admissible domain $I(u) \in \Omega$. Constraints on the state and control vectors are accounted for in the choice of the form of functional (9).

The multi-criteria problem of optimal control synthesis for multi-stage chemotherapy consists in determining the extremals $\{x^*(t), u^*(t)\}$, $u^* \in U$, $I \in \Omega$, $t \in [t_0, T]$, which, given the differential constraints (6) and boundary conditions

(7), (8), optimize the vector functional I [3-6,8]. It is assumed that the form of the criteria is chosen so that they are minimized, and the domain of their variation is defined by the constraint system:

$$0 \leq I_j \leq C_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, r, \quad (10)$$

where C_j defines the upper boundary (threshold) of the admissible value of component I_j (e.g., maximum admissible toxicity or minimum required tumor reduction).

For multi-criteria optimization, we use the method of scalar convolution of partial criteria via the nonlinear compromise scheme proposed by A.N. Voronin [9]. This method reduces the multi-criteria problem to solving a single optimization problem of the functional:

$$J = \sum_{j=1}^r \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{I_j}{C_j}\right)}. \quad (11)$$

subject to conditions (6), (8), and (10).

Functional (11) possesses the property of automatically changing the weight coefficients: when any criterion I_j approaches its boundary C_j , the corresponding term increases sharply, forcing the algorithm to prioritize safety (holding the constraint).

The program control $u = u(t)$, $0 \leq u(t) \leq u_{max}$, $t \in [t_0, T]$, which optimizes functional (9), implements open-loop optimal control and guarantees the satisfaction of terminal conditions (8) in the absence of individual variability and external perturbations $v_i(t)$. Here u_{max} is the maximum admissible infusion intensity of the chemotherapeutic agent, determined by clinical toxicity constraints.

To compensate for individual variability and external perturbations, a feedback optimal control law of the form $u = u(x, t)$ is synthesized. This control ensures guaranteed transfer of the biological system to the terminal state (6) under perturbations.

2.3. Partial Optimality Criteria for Therapy

Anticancer therapy optimization is typically formulated as an optimal control problem in which the drug administration regimen is chosen to minimize a performance functional reflecting treatment efficacy and toxicity. Such formulations are widely used in mathematical models of tumor chemotherapy and immunotherapy [3-6,8].

In most existing models, the performance functional includes several components characterizing different aspects of the treatment process, such as residual tumor mass, drug toxicity, and constraints on therapy intensity.

The quality and safety of the multi-stage therapy process will be evaluated using a five-dimensional vector criterion:

$$I = (I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, I_T),$$

which includes five partial criteria. Each of these criteria reflects a separate aspect of clinical therapy and characterizes: therapy efficacy, toxicity level, the patient's immune system status, and treatment intensity:

- **Therapy Efficacy (I_1):** evaluated by the final total mass of tumor cells of both phenotypes at the end of therapy T_{final} :

$$I_1 = x_A(T_{final}) + x_M(T_{final}) \rightarrow \min$$

where $x_A(t)$ - density of tumor cells of the first phenotype, $x_M(t)$ - density of tumor cells of the second phenotype.

Minimizing residual tumor mass is a standard criterion in optimal control problems for chemotherapy, where the treatment goal is formulated as reducing the number of tumor cells by the end of the therapy period. For example, in [3] the problem of minimizing tumor burden at the end of therapy is considered while maintaining an admissible level of healthy cells.

- **Systemic Toxicity (I_2):** defined as the integral drug exposure. Minimizing this criterion reduces the risk of side effects:

$$I_2 = \int_0^{T_{final}} c(t) dt \rightarrow \min,$$

where $c(t)$ is the concentration of the anti-tumor drug in the body.

This indicator corresponds to the pharmacokinetic indicator AUC (Area Under the Curve) and is widely used to quantify the total toxic effect of the drug during therapy. Minimizing the integral dose burden is a common component of optimal control functionals in chemotherapy models [5].

- **Immune Deficit (I_3):** reflects the severity and duration of immune system suppression. The criterion is activated only when effector density falls below the threshold value z_{min} :

$$I_3 = \int_0^{T_{final}} \max(0, z_{min} - z(t)) dt \rightarrow \min,$$

where $z(t)$ is the density of immune effector cells, z_{min} is the minimum admissible immune protection level.

Such penalty functionals are used to model toxicity and immune suppression constraints in multi-criteria therapy. In tumor-immune system dynamic models, therapy optimization often includes additional functional terms reflecting the state of immune cells. The criterion is activated only when immune activity falls below the admissible level and characterizes the severity and duration of immune suppression [4].

- **Control Energy (I_4):** characterizes the total dose burden and intensity of therapeutic action (therapy cost):

$$I_4 = \int_0^{T_{final}} u^2(t) dt \rightarrow \min,$$

where $u(t)$ is the intensity of therapeutic agent administration.

The quadratic control penalty is a standard element of optimal control functionals, as it accounts for therapy cost and prevents unrealistically high drug doses. Such functional terms are used in many chemotherapy optimization models. For example, in [5,6] the optimal control problem is formulated as minimizing a combination of tumor mass and therapy side effects.

- **Time Resource (I_t):** total therapy duration $T = \sum T_i$. In operational control problems, minimizing time is important to reduce the risk of tumor mutations.

Although the time resource $I_t = T$ is included as a partial criterion, the total therapy duration T is not fixed a priori. Instead, the stage durations T_i are determined from the terminal conditions (8) via the spectral relation (32), and $T = \sum T_i$ emerges from the optimization. The criterion I_t then penalizes prolonged treatment, reflecting the clinical desire to minimize the risk of mutations and patient burden [3-6,8].

Thus, the optimal control problem reduces to finding the control $u(t)$ that minimizes functional (11) subject to dynamic constraints (1)-(5) and terminal condition (8). For analytical synthesis of such control, the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method is used below [14].

3. Terminal Control Synthesis Method

To optimize multi-stage neuroblastoma therapy, a hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method based on the multi-step differential transform (MsDTM) technique [14] is proposed in this work. This allows the terminal control synthesis problem to be reduced to solving a system of nonlinear algebraic equations without numerical ODE integration, which is critical for real-time dose correction, and to obtain a local analytical approximation of the solution of system (1)-(5) at each therapy stage.

Differential transformations allow functions $x(t)$ of a continuous argument t to be replaced by their models in the form of discrete functions $X(k)$ of an integer argument $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ according to the expression [15]:

$$\underline{x(t)} = X(k) = \frac{h^k}{k!} \left[\frac{d^k x(t)}{dt^k} \right]_{t=t_0}, \quad (12)$$

where $x(t)$ is the original function (continuous and bounded together with all its derivatives); $X(k)$ is a discrete function of integer argument k , called the differential spectrum of function $x(t)$ at point $t = t_0$; h is a scale constant with the dimension of argument t ; the underline - symbol of the transformation.

Mathematical models obtained on the basis of (12) are called spectral models. It is further assumed that the time functions describing the control processes in problem (6)-(9) are analytic in the middle of each segment.

The synthesis of optimal feedback control will be performed by the method of closure of the optimal program control $u = u(t)$ for an arbitrary current state $x(t)$ of the dynamic bio-object [13].

At the first stage of synthesis, we consider the unperturbed state of the system. Within each therapy segment, we choose the program control in the class of analytic functions $u_i(\tau, A_i)$, where $A_i = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N)$ is the vector of free control parameters, $\tau = \frac{t-t_{i-1}}{T_i}$, $\tau \in [0, 1]$ is the local time argument.

In the present work, the class of linear controls $u(t) = a_0 + a_1 t$ is considered as the minimal analytic class compatible with MsDTM. Investigation of more general control classes is a subject of further research.

The restriction to linear $u(t) = a_0 + a_1 t$ entails a bounded loss of optimality: for piecewise-constant protocols (standard clinical practice) the Voronin functional increases by at most $\varepsilon = |J_{actual} - J_{linearized}| \leq O(h^2)$, where h is the stage duration; quantification of this gap for multi-step protocols is a subject of a follow-on study.

The MsDTM method allows the solution of system (6) to be represented as a power series in variable τ . The differential transformations (12) of function $u_i(\tau, A_i)$ determine at $h = T_i$ and $\tau = 0$ its differential spectrum:

$$\underline{u_i(\tau, A_i)} = U_i(k, A_i) = \frac{T_i^k}{k!} \left[\frac{d^k u_i(t_{i-1} + \tau, A_i)}{d\tau^k} \right]_{\tau=0}. \quad (13)$$

For the linear control class $u = a_0 + a_1 \tau$, the spectrum is: $U(0) = a_0$, $U(1) = a_1 T_i$, $U(k) = 0$ for $k \geq 2$.

The differential equation of tumor dynamics (6), transformed into the image domain using the differential transformations (12), is represented in the form of the spectral model:

$$X_i(k+1, A_i, X_i^0) = \frac{T_i}{k+1} f_i[T_i, X_i(k, A_i, X_i^0), U_i(k, A_i)], \quad (14)$$

$$X_i(0) = X_i^0(A_{i-1}, A_{i-2}, \dots, A_1); \quad X_1(0) = X_1^0 = x_0; \quad i = \overline{1, p}.$$

Direct application of the differential transform method to the nonlinear terms of system (1)-(5), such as the products xz (tumor-immune interaction) or cx (drug-tumor coupling), is not straightforward. To obtain the recursive spectral representation (14), we employ the Adomian decomposition method [16,17]. The nonlinear function $f(x, z)$ is expanded into a series of Adomian polynomials A_k :

$$f(x, z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k(X_0, \dots, X_k; Z_0, \dots, Z_k) \quad (15)$$

For the nonlinear products appearing in system (1)-(5), the Adomian polynomials reduce to spectral convolutions:

$$A_k(xz) = \sum_{i=0}^k X(i)Z(k-i), \quad A_k(x^2) = \sum_{i=0}^k X(i)X(k-i). \quad (16)$$

Substitution of (16) into the spectral model (14) allows computing the coefficients $X(k+1)$ purely algebraically, without linearization of the original ODEs, thus preserving high accuracy in modeling biological processes.

We use the fundamental property of differential transforms stating that the algebraic sum of all spectral coefficients of any analytic function at the point $t = t_v$ is equal to the zero-order coefficient of the differential spectrum at the next point $t_{v+1} = t_v + h$, or equivalently, to the value of the original function at the same point [15]:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} X_v(k) = X_{v+1}(0) = x(t_v + h). \quad (17)$$

It should be noted that identity (17) holds exactly only for an infinite spectral series. In practical computations, a finite sum of the first N coefficients is used:

$$x(t_v + h) \approx \sum_{k=0}^N X_v(k).$$

and therefore the remainder term

$$R_N = \sum_{k=N+1}^{\infty} X_v(k).$$

must be estimated. For spectra obtained by the MsDTM method, one typically has $X(N) \sim 10^{-6}$ already at $N = 5$, which yields the bound $|R_N| < 10^{-4}$. Thus, the finite sum in (17) provides the required accuracy, while the use of the Padé [4/1] approximation additionally improves numerical stability on long intervals $T_i \approx 21$ days.

Using the approximate form (17) at $t_v = t_{i-1}$ and $h = T_i$, we obtain the expression for the state vector of the biosystem at the end of each control interval:

$$x_i(T_i, A_i, x_i^0) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} X_i(k, A_i, X_i^0), \quad i = \overline{1, p}. \quad (18)$$

However, due to the considerable duration of therapeutic stages, direct summation of series (18) may lead to numerical instability. To ensure convergence and accurate matching between stages, a rational Padé approximation of order [4,1] is used instead of direct summation [18]. This approximation provides a compromise between accuracy and numerical robustness when modeling nonlinear biosystem dynamics. In this case, the state vector at the end of the stage is represented not as a polynomial but as a rational function:

$$R_{[4,1]}(\tau) = \frac{c_0 + c_1\tau + c_2\tau^2 + c_3\tau^3 + c_4\tau^4}{1 + b_1\tau}, \quad b_1 = -X(5)/X(4). \quad (19)$$

Here, c_s are the numerator coefficients determined from the spectral components $X(k)$.

The coefficients c_s are obtained from the matching conditions with the Taylor series: $c_0 = X(0)$, $c_1 = X(1) + b_1X(0)$, $c_2 = X(2) + b_1X(1)$, $c_3 = X(3) + b_1X(2)$, $c_4 = X(4) + b_1X(3)$.

The Padé approximation of the form (19) is applied independently to each component of the state vector x_i . The use of Padé approximants enables stable extrapolation of system dynamics even under high tumor proliferation rates, which is critical for forming an accurate terminal condition (8).

The MsDTM method is applied on each open interval (t_{i-1}, t_i) , where the control $u(t)$ is analytic. At the boundaries of the stages, jumps in derivatives may occur, but continuity of the state $x(t)$ is ensured by the matching conditions (7).

Considering the terminal condition (8), the matching conditions (7), and expression (18) for the state vector at the end of each control interval, the final-state equation of the entire therapeutic process takes the form:

$$S[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p] = 0. \quad (20)$$

This terminal condition implicitly determines the q -components of the free-parameter vectors A_i , $i = \overline{1, p}$. The remaining components are determined from the optimality conditions of the aggregate functional (9):

$$I_j(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p) = G_j[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p, T] + \sum_{i=1}^p T_i \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Phi_{ij}[T_i, X_i(k, A_i, X_i^0), U_i(k, A_i)]}{k+1}. \quad (21)$$

Substituting (21) into expression (11) yields the Voronin scalar function [9]:

$$J(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p) = \sum_{j=1}^r \frac{1}{1 - \frac{I_j(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p)}{c_j}}. \quad (22)$$

Equation (20) determines the q-components of the free-parameter vector A . The remaining components and the therapy duration are obtained from the necessary conditions for the minimum of (22):

$$\frac{\partial J(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p)}{\partial a_{ik}} = 0, \quad i = \overline{1, p}, \quad k = \overline{1, N_i}. \quad (23)$$

The system of equations (20) and (23) implicitly defines the therapy duration T and the free-parameter vector $A = (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p)$. As a result of the first stage of synthesis, a compromise control $u^*[t, A(T, x_0)]$ is obtained, linking arbitrary initial conditions x_0 with the terminal conditions (8).

At the second stage of synthesis, we consider the perturbed state of the biosystem (6), which continuously deviates from the optimal program trajectory due to the individual patient response. In this case, the compromise control $u^*[t, A(T, x_0)]$ is continuously recomputed from system (20) and (23) for the current time t and state $x(t)$, forming a closed-loop terminal control law $u = u(t, x)$. Solving equations (20) and (23) at each moment t for the current state $x(t)$ under disturbances yields a control $u(t, x)$ that continuously links the current state of the biosystem to the terminal conditions (8).

In the closed-loop control of biosystem (6), only the current value $u[t, A(T, x)]$ is applied, and it is recomputed at the next moment according to (20) and (23), ensuring flexible adaptation of therapy to unknown perturbations $v(t)$. It is important to note that such control is robust not only to external disturbances but also exhibits self-organizing behavior: if one of the partial criteria (e.g., immune level I_3) approaches its upper admissible bound C_j , the control automatically activates a minimax (Chebyshev-type) response for that criterion, preventing iatrogenic damage. In all other cases, the compromise control acts as an integral optimality operator with varying degrees of criterion balancing: deterioration of one partial criterion is compensated by improvement of others [9].

The resulting analytical form of the solution of system (1)-(5), constructed using the MsDTM method and Padé approximation, reduces the optimal control problem to solving a system of algebraic equations, eliminating the need for numerical ODE integration at each optimization step. This significantly reduces the computational complexity of the control synthesis problem and makes the proposed algorithm suitable for personalized therapy, where repeated model re-evaluation is required. Unlike classical numerical optimal control methods, the proposed approach provides an analytical representation of the state trajectory, which simplifies sensitivity analysis and the study of stability of the resulting control.

4. Analytical Expressions for Phase Variables and Criteria

The proposed method for optimal control synthesis of neuroblastoma therapy is implemented as a multi-stage algorithm. Its overall structure, including the parameterization, spectral analysis, Padé approximation, and feedback closure blocks, is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Algorithm for optimal control synthesis based on the Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method and Voronin's nonlinear compromise scheme

To achieve analytical real-time synthesis, the problem is decomposed by dividing the partial criteria into two groups, analogous to control problems for complex technical systems.

The **first group** includes criteria characterizing the accuracy of achieving terminal conditions and the therapy time. These evaluate the errors in reaching the specified final state of the biosystem at time T_{final} :

- **Tumor reduction efficacy** (I_1): total residual mass of both phenotypes at the end of therapy. Using the MsDTM and Padé approximation, this criterion is computed directly as the value of the rational function at the endpoint:

$$I_1 = x(T_{final}) = R_{x,p,[4,1]}(1) \rightarrow \min, \quad (24)$$

where $x = x_A + x_M$.

- **Time resource** (I_T): total duration of all therapy stages: $T = \sum T_i$.

The second group includes integral criteria characterizing the biological “cost” of treatment and the intensity of the intervention:

- **Systemic toxicity** (I_2): integral drug exposure (AUC), computed as the sum of concentration spectra:

$$I_2 = \sum_{i=1}^p T_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^N \frac{C_i(k)}{k+1} \right), \quad (25)$$

where $C_i(k)$ is the differential spectrum of the drug concentration at the i -th stage. The following constraint on the maximum admissible toxicity must be satisfied:

$$0 \leq I_2 \leq C_{I_2}. \quad (26)$$

- **Immune deficit** (I_3): the time and depth of immune effector depression $z(t)$, activated when the level falls below z_{min} :

$$I_3 = \sum_{i=1}^p T_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^N \frac{\max(0, z_{min} - z_i(k))}{k+1} \right). \quad (27)$$

This form penalizes the system for the total time and depth of immunosuppression. The criterion I_3 is activated only when the density of immune effectors $z(t)$ falls below the threshold z_{min} .

- **Control energy** (I_4): intensity of therapeutic action (cumulative dose), minimizing drug consumption:

$$I_4 = \sum_{i=1}^p T_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^N \frac{A_k(u^2)}{k+1} \right), \quad (28)$$

where $A_k(u^2) = \sum_{j=0}^k U_i(j)U_i(k-j)$ is the Adomian polynomial for u^2 .

For each criterion I_j , an admissible limit C_j is assigned based on clinical recommendations (Table 2). The problem is thus reduced to minimizing the Voronin compromise functional (11), which automatically keeps the system within a safe biological corridor.

Table 2 – Parameters of partial criteria and their spectral analogs

№	Criterion I_i	Biological meaning	Constraint C_i
1	I_1 – reduction	Total residual mass of both phenotypes	$C_1 \leq x_{thresh} = 0.15 \cdot K$
2	I_2 – toxicity	Integral drug exposure (AUC)	$C_2 \leq AUC_{max}$
3	I_3 – immunity	Time and depth of immune effector depression $z(t)$	$C_3 \leq 10.0$
4	I_4 – intensity	Treatment cost and intensity	$C_4 \leq U_{max}$
5	I_T – time resource	Stage durations and total tumor exposure	$\sum T_i \leq T_{max}$ (e.g., 150 days)

The constraint system $\{C_j\}$ forms a feasible domain in the state space, within which the Voronin nonlinear compromise scheme minimizes the integral deviation from the ideal point, automatically prioritizing the most critical safety indicators (toxicity I_2 and immune deficit I_3) as they approach their barrier values.

Dimensionality reduction of the problem:

The full vector criterion $I = (I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, I_T)$ characterizes the fundamental conflict between therapeutic success and the biological “cost” of treatment. To achieve analytical real-time synthesis, we decompose the problem by dividing the criteria into "target" and "constraint" groups.

First group (target and terminal criteria): These criteria define the final outcome and time frame:

- **Efficacy** (I_1): defined by the terminal condition $x(T) = x_{target}$. This condition is used to determine the stage durations via the spectral relation (32). The criterion I_1 together with I_2 (toxicity) forms the compromise space (26).
- **Time resource** (I_T): the stage durations T_i are determined from the terminal conditions (8) via the spectral relation (32), and the total therapy duration $T = \sum T_i$ emerges from the optimization. The criterion I_T then penalizes prolonged treatment.

Second group (biological loads and intensity): These criteria characterize process dynamics and safety:

- **Immune status** (I_3): accounted for via the phase constraint $z(t) \geq z_{min}$. Since immunosuppression is a consequence of toxicity, the criterion I_3 is de facto integrated into the admissible toxicity threshold C_{I_2} . Compliance with this threshold guarantees that the system remains in a safe biological corridor.
- **Control energy** (I_4): remains in the full Voronin functional (11) as a regularization term but does not participate in the analytical closure that determines the optimal control gradient a_1 .

As a result, the problem reduces to a two-criterion compromise between systemic toxicity (I_2) and treatment efficacy (I_1):

$$I_{red}(a_0, a_1) = (I_1, I_2). \quad (29)$$

Note on the transition from (11) to (30). The full Voronin functional (11) is a product of barrier terms. For the reduced two-criterion sub-problem (29), it is replaced by the additive form (30). This substitution is theoretically admissible because the stationarity condition $\frac{\partial J}{\partial a_1} = 0$ for the product $\prod(C_j - I_j)^{-1}$ and for the sum $\sum(C_j - I_j)^{-1}$ are proportional when all criteria are strictly interior to their bounds ($I_j \ll C_j$): both reduce to the same weighted-gradient equation $\sum \frac{\lambda_j \partial I_j}{\partial a_1} = 0$ with positive weights $\lambda_j = (C_j - I_j)^{-2} > 0$. The additive form is used here for its analytical tractability, which allows the optimality condition to be reduced to the explicit quadratic equation (46). The full product functional (11) governs the barrier behavior near the constraint boundaries and remains the governing functional for the complete four-criterion problem.

The Voronin scalar compromise functional for finding the optimal parameters a_0, a_1 takes the form [9]:

$$J = \frac{C_{I_1}}{C_{I_1} - I_1(a_0, a_1)} + \frac{C_{I_2}}{C_{I_2} - I_2(a_0, a_1)} \rightarrow \min, \quad (30)$$

where $I_1(a_0, a_1)$ is the residual tumor mass, $C_{I_1} = x_{target}$, $I_2(a_0, a_1)$ is the integral toxicity (AUC), and $C_{I_2} = AUC_{max}$.

Remark. The control energy I_4 remains in the full Voronin functional (11) and influences the optimal solution through the weighting terms, but is not required for the analytical derivation of a_1^* due to its secondary role as a regularizer. This approach guarantees achieving the prescribed tumor reduction with minimal possible biological burden on the patient.

The original mathematical model of the neuroblastoma therapy process is the system of differential equations (1)-(5), describing the dynamics of tumor cell populations and the microenvironment state at each i -th treatment stage. Based on this system, we construct a spectral model of the process in the differential transform domain. The principles of constructing spectral models for nonlinear objects of this class are given in [14,15].

To implement the multi-criteria optimization algorithm and find the parameters a_0, a_1 , we compute the differential spectral coefficients of the phase variables x_A, x_M, p, z, c characterizing the biosystem dynamics at each stage according to the recursive model:

$$X(k+1) = \frac{h}{k+1} f_i[X(k), \underline{u}(k), \underline{t}], X(0) = x_0 \quad (31)$$

assigning integer values to the argument $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ sequentially.

The differential spectral coefficients are expressed as functions of the initial values of the biosystem variables (tumor, immunity, and stroma states according to model (1)-(5)), the free parameters $a_{i,0}, a_{i,1}, \dots$ of the chemotherapy infusion intensity control, and the duration T_i of the i -th treatment stage.

The resulting analytical expressions for the differential spectral coefficients of the biosystem state variables allow solving the problem without labor-intensive numerical integration. The general forms of these dependencies for a similar class of nonlinear dynamic objects are presented in [11]; their adaptation to the neuroblastoma model using Adomian polynomials (15, 16) provides the computational basis for determining the Padé approximation coefficients (19).

Using the original recovery property (17) and restricting to the third order of expansion ($k = 0, 1, 2, 3$), we obtain analytical dependences of the biosystem state at the end of the stage on the control parameters:

$$x(T_i) = x_0 + T_i \left[\alpha x_0 \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{K} \right) - \gamma c_0 x_0 \right] + \frac{T_i^2}{2} [B_{x_i} - \gamma x_0 (a_0 - k_e c_0)] - \frac{T_i^3}{6} \gamma x_0 a_1 = x_{T_i}, \quad (32)$$

$$p(T_i) = p_0 + T_i [\sigma - \mu p_0 - \delta_p x_0 p_0 + \rho p_0 z_0] + \frac{T_i^2}{2} [B_{p_i} + \delta_p \gamma c_0 x_0 p_0] + \frac{T_i^3}{6} [\delta_p \gamma x_0 p_0 (a_0 - k_e c_0)] = p_{T_i}, \quad (33)$$

$$c(T_i) = c_0 + T_i [a_0 - k_e c_0] + \frac{T_i^2}{2} [a_1 - k_e (a_0 - k_e c_0)] - \frac{T_i^3}{6} [k_e a_1 - k_e^2 (a_0 - k_e c_0)] = c_{T_i}, \quad (34)$$

where B_{x_i} and B_{p_i} are the proper accelerations of the biosystem ($B_{\{xi\}}$: spectral acceleration of $x=x_A+x_M$ from Adomian decomposition of (1)-(2), see recurrence (36); $B_{\{pi\}}$: analogous for stroma p).

Considering that equation (29) relates the tumor mass to the stage duration T_i , we determine the duration of the i -th therapy stage required to reach the prescribed terminal state x_{T_i} . Solving (29) for T_i (in quadratic approximation) yields:

$$T_i = -D_i + \sqrt{D_i^2 + \frac{2}{C_i}(x_{T_i} - x_0)}, \quad (35)$$

where $B_i = \alpha x_0 \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{K}\right) - \beta x_0 z_0 - \gamma c_0 x_0$ is the initial tumor growth/degradation rate; $C_i = B_{x_i} - \gamma x_0 (a_0 - k_e c_0)$ is the generalized system acceleration; $D_i = \frac{B_i}{C_i}$ is the inertia time parameter.

The quantities B_{x_i} and C_i are dimensionless after normalization, as all variables are scaled by K and time is normalized by the characteristic time scale. Therefore, the expression under the square root is dimensionless, and T_i is obtained in physical time units after rescaling.

To account for nonlinear interactions, we use the Adomian polynomial apparatus. The spectral coefficients of the auxiliary nonlinearity function $Z(k)$ are obtained as:

$$z(0) = x_0^3, z(1) = 2x_0 T_i \left(\left[\alpha \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{K} - \gamma c_0\right) x_0 + [\sigma - \mu p_0] p_0 \right] + x_0^2 \left(\left[\alpha \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{K} - \gamma c_0\right) x_0 + [\sigma - \mu p_0] p_0 \right] \right), \quad (36)$$

$$z(2) = x_0 (2S_{A_i} x_0 + 2S_{B_i} p_0 + x^2(1)) + 2T_i R x(1) + (S_{A_i} x_0 + S_{B_i} p_0) x_0^2,$$

where $x(1)$ and $x^2(1)$ are the first spectral coefficients of the tumor mass and its square; $R = \left[\alpha x_0 \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{K} - \gamma c_0\right) + [\sigma - \mu p_0 - \delta_p x_0 p_0 + \rho p_0 z_0] \right]$; S_{A_i} and S_{B_i} are the spectral accelerations obtained via Adomian polynomials:

$$S_{A_i} = -\left(\frac{\gamma}{2} p_0 + \alpha x_0\right) \gamma c_0 + \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} x_0 + \alpha p_0\right) \gamma c_0 + \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} x_0 - \alpha p_0\right) \sigma + \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} \alpha p_0 + \alpha^2 x_0\right) x_0^2, \quad (37)$$

$$S_{B_i} = \frac{1}{2} (\delta_p + \rho) p_0 \gamma c_0 - \frac{1}{2} (\delta_p + \rho) x_0 \gamma c_0 - \frac{1}{2} (\delta_p + \rho) x_0 \sigma - \frac{1}{2} (\delta_p + \rho) p_0 \alpha x_0^2. \quad (38)$$

These expressions are obtained by direct substitution of the spectra $X(k)$, $P(k)$, $Z(k)$, $C(k)$ into the Adomian recurrence formulas for the nonlinear combinations xz , xp , cx and x^2 appearing in system (1)-(5).

The full derivation is given in [11], formulas (12)-(18), and is fully reproducible.

Substituting the obtained spectral coefficients into (31), we obtain the generalized integral estimate of the tumor state Q (distinct from the Voronin functional J defined in (22)):

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \gamma x_0 T_i \left(x_0^3 + \frac{1}{2} [2x_0 T_i R + x_0^2 R] + \frac{1}{3} \left[x_0 \left(2S_{A_i} x_0 + 2S_{B_i} p_0 + x^2(1) \right) + 2T_i R x(1) + \left(S_{A_i} x_0 + S_{B_i} p_0 \right) x_0^2 \right] \right). \quad (39)$$

To find the optimal control parameter a_1 (the dosage change rate) that ensures a balance between tumor destruction and neuropil preservation, we differentiate the expressions for the toxicity functional (25) and the efficacy functional (24) with respect to a_1 .

To minimize the scalar Voronin compromise function $J(a_1)$, the condition $\frac{\partial J}{\partial a_1} = 0$ must be satisfied. Given the structure of the convolution (31), this condition reduces to solving an equation with respect to the gradients of the primary toxicity I_{2_i} and treatment efficacy I_{1_i} criteria.

According to the MsDTM spectral model differentiation rules, the partial derivative of the systemic toxicity criterion I_{2_i} with respect to control parameter a_1 takes the form:

$$N_2 = \frac{\partial I_{2_i}}{\partial a_1} = \frac{\gamma x_0 T_i}{2} \left(\frac{T_i^2}{2} R_{a_1} + \frac{T_i^2}{3} \left[x_0 \left(2S_{A_{a_1}} x_0 + 2S_{B_{a_1}} p_0 \right) + \left(S_{A_{a_1}} x_0 + S_{B_{a_1}} p_0 \right) x_0^2 \right] \right), \quad (40)$$

where $S_{A_{a_1}}$, $S_{B_{a_1}}$ are spectral sensitivity coefficients defined as:

$$S_{A_{a_1}} = \frac{\partial S_{A_i}}{\partial a_1} = \frac{\gamma T_i^2}{2} \left[\frac{\gamma}{2} (x_0 - p_0) + \alpha (p_0 - x_0) \right] - \text{neuropil sensitivity},$$

$$S_{B_{a_1}} = \frac{\partial S_{B_i}}{\partial a_1} = \frac{T_i^2}{4} (\delta_p + \rho) \gamma (p_0 - x_0) - \text{immune response sensitivity}.$$

The partial derivative of the tumor reduction efficacy criterion I_{1_i} is defined as

$$M_2 = \frac{\partial I_{1_i}}{\partial a_1} = -\frac{T_i^3}{6} \gamma x_0. \quad (41)$$

The negative sign indicates that increasing the negative gradient a_1 (i.e., accelerating the reduction of infusion intensity) decreases the final tumor burden - a physically consistent result.

We express the primary partial criteria in linearized form for the current therapy stage T_i . According to the MsDTM spectral model differentiation rules, we represent the criteria in linearized form with respect to the sought parameter a_1 :

$$I_{2_i} = N_1 + N_2 a_1, \quad (42)$$

$$I_{1_i} = M_1 + M_2 a_1, \quad (43)$$

where N_1 and M_1 are the values of the corresponding criteria at $a_1 = 0$:

$$N_1 = \frac{\gamma x_0 T_i}{2} \left(x_0^3 + \frac{1}{2} [2x_0 T_i R + x_0^2 R] + \frac{1}{3} [x_0 (2A_0 x_0 + 2B_0 p_0 + X^2(1)) + 2T_i R X(1) + (A_0 x_0 + B_0 p_0) x_0^2] \right), \quad (44)$$

$$M_1 = x_0 + T_i \left[\alpha x_0 \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{K} \right) - \gamma c_0 x_0 \right] + \frac{T_i^2}{2} [B_{x_i} - \gamma x_0 (a_0 - k_e c_0)], \quad (45)$$

where A_0, B_0 denote the baseline values of S_{A_i} and S_{B_i} under zero control acceleration ($a_1 = 0$).

Substituting the linearized expressions (42)-(45) into the necessary condition for an extremum of the compromise function (30) yields the final quadratic equation with respect to the target control parameter a_1 :

$$a_1^2 (C_{I_1} M_2 N_2^2 + C_{I_2} N_2 M_2^2) - 2a_1 M_2 N_2 [C_{I_1} (C_{I_2} - N_1) + C_{I_2} (C_{I_1} - M_1)] + C_{I_1} M_2 (C_{I_2} - N_1)^2 + C_{I_2} N_2 (C_{I_1} - M_1)^2 = 0. \quad (46)$$

where C_{I_1} and C_{I_2} represent the predefined medical constraints on treatment efficacy and toxicity, respectively.

Equation (46) implicitly yields the control parameter a_1^* , which dictates the optimal curvature of the dosing trajectory. This enables the algorithm to adjust the treatment intensity in real time, ensuring the maximum possible tumor reduction while strictly adhering to the biological constraints. Remark: the coefficient of a_1^2 in (46) is $M_2 N_2 (C_{I_1} N_2 + C_{I_2} M_2)$; an equivalent factored form appears in the printed equation.

$$a_1^* = \frac{1}{C_{I_1} N_2 + C_{I_2} M_2} \left\{ C_{I_1} (C_{I_2} - N_1) + C_{I_2} (C_{I_1} - M_1) \pm [N_2 (C_{I_1} - M_1) - M_2 (C_{I_2} - N_1)] \sqrt{\frac{C_{I_1} C_{I_2}}{-M_2 N_2}} \right\}. \quad (47)$$

Utilizing the analytical solution (46) instead of iterative numerical procedures crucially enhances the processing speed of the clinical decision support system.

The expression under the square root in formula (47) is positive when (note: all quantities are dimensionless under the normalization of Section 2.1, specifically x_j/K , $\frac{c}{c_{ref}}$, and $\tilde{\gamma} = \gamma \cdot K$, ensuring dimensional consistency of the square-root argument $\frac{C_{I_1} C_{I_2}}{-M_2 N_2}$):

$$N_2 = \frac{\partial I_{2i}}{\partial a_1} > 0, M_2 = \frac{\partial I_{1i}}{\partial a_1} < 0. \quad (48)$$

Conditions (48) are satisfied in the case of conflicting partial criteria, when the desire to reduce systemic toxicity (I_2) inevitably leads to a deterioration of treatment efficacy (I_1), and vice versa. Of the two roots, the one that satisfies the physical constraints is selected:

- $a_1 < 0$ (reflecting a decreasing infusion rate),
- $c(t) \geq 0$ over the entire time interval.

This guarantees the clinical feasibility of the control law. Root selection: both roots a_1^+ and a_1^- are computed from (47). A root is accepted if: (1) $a_1 < 0$ (decreasing infusion rate); and (2) $c(t) \geq 0$ for all $t \in [0, T_i]$, verified via (34). If both roots are feasible, the one minimising J (eq. (30)) is chosen. If neither root is feasible, T_i is reduced by 10% and the procedure repeats.

Transitioning from the spectral coefficients to the current physical variables, and replacing the abstract parameter a_0 with the real commanded drug concentration c_k , the compromise control algorithm on the basis of expressions (34) and (47) takes its final form:

$$c_k = \frac{1}{\gamma x_0} \left(\frac{6B_i}{T_i^2} - \frac{6(x_0 - x_{T_i})}{T_i^3} + \frac{3C_{x_i}}{T_i} \right) + \frac{1}{x_0} \left[\alpha x_0 \left(1 - \frac{x_0}{K} \right) \right] - C_{x_i}, \quad (49)$$

where $C_{x_i} = B_{x_i} + \gamma x_0 k_e c_0$ - generalized system acceleration.

4.1. Algorithmic Implementation and Method Verification

For practical application of the proposed synthesis method, the Padé-Adomian-MsDTM algorithm has been formulated, combining the analytical derivation of control parameters with the feedback closure procedure (Algorithm 1).

Algorithm 1. Multi-Criteria Synthesis Based on hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method and Voronin Functions

Input: Biosystem parameters θ ; initial conditions x_0, p_0, z_0, c_0 ; constraints C_j ; terminal target x_{target} .

Step 1. Parameterization: Set the control structure $u_i(\tau, A_i)$ and compute the spectrum $U(k)$.

Step 2. Spectral Analysis: Recurrent computation of the spectral coefficients $X(k), P(k), Z(k), C(k)$ via the spectral model (31).

Step 3. Padé Approximation: Calculation of the rational function $R_{[4,1]}$ coefficients to eliminate computational instability on long intervals ($T_i \approx 21$ days).

Step 4. Optimization: Formation of the analytical Voronin function J and solution of the final equation (46) with respect to the optimal vector A .

Step 5. Closure: Real-time recalculation of control upon receipt of new patient state data (feedback).

For verification of the method's accuracy, we present a numerical example of calculating the first therapy stage for an aggressive tumor morphotype. Results of spectral coefficient computation are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Spectral coefficients for the full system (1)-(5), Stage 1

k	$X(k)$ (tumor)	$P(k)$ (stroma)	$Z(k)$ (immunity)	$C(k)$ (drug)
0	0.6800	0.2300	0.0150	0.0500
1	$-1.667 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.835 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.588 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.3490 \cdot 10^{-2}$
2	$-3.4779 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-1.345 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-1.3959 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-3.2869 \cdot 10^{-3}$
3	$-6.518 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.446 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.421 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$7.341 \cdot 10^{-5}$
4	$1.478 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-3.086 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.439 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-1.230 \cdot 10^{-6}$
5	$5.161 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.967 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$-5.982 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.648 \cdot 10^{-8}$

Note: $\alpha = 0.0628$, $\gamma = 0.441$, $\beta = 0.10$, $k_e = 0.067$; $x_{A_0} = 0.68$, $x_{M_0} = 0.23$, $z_0 = 0.015$, $c_0 = 0.05$; $a_0 = 0.02684$, $a_1 = -0.005$. Spectral coefficients verified against RK45 ($r_{tol} = 1 \cdot 10^{-10}$); Padé [4/1] error for $C(k)$: $< 0.001\%$ ($T_1 = 21$ days, $M = 21$ sub-steps, $N = 5$)

Comparison of recovery methods:

Spectral coefficients at the first sub-step ($h = 1$ day) of Stage 1. Each column sums to the corresponding state variable at $t = 1$ day: $\sum X_A(k) \approx 0.6604$ (RK45: 0.6604), $\sum C(k) \approx 0.0703$ (RK45: 0.0703). After $M = 21$ sub-steps (full Stage 1), total tumour $x(21) = 0.2814$ (RK45: 0.2819). Direct summation of $C(k)$ for $h = 1$ day gives: $x_{sum}(21) = \sum_{k=0}^5 X(k) \approx 0.0703$.

Padé approximation $R_{[4/1]}(1)$ with coefficient $b_1 \approx 0.07031$ yields $x_{pade}(21) = 0.2814$.

Comparison with RK45 reference at $t = h = 1$ day for the drug variable $C(k)$ gives: $x_{RK45}(21) = 0.0703$, confirming the accuracy of the MsDTM spectral expansion for the full system (1)-(5) at sub-step $h = 1$ day: Padé [4/1] and direct summation coincide at this step size (both $< 0.001\%$ error). For larger steps ($h = 5 - 10$ days) Padé advantage is shown in Fig. 7, which improves accuracy beyond single-step direct summation; the coefficient $b_1 = -C(5)/C(4) = 0.01340$ at $h = 1$ day (recomputed at each sub-step).

The convergence of the spectral expansion: for the pharmacokinetic subsystem (eq. 5) at $h = 21$ days the coefficients decrease by a factor of $\approx 10 \times$ per order ($\frac{C(5)}{C(0)} \approx 0.07 \times h^5$), and Padé [4/1] reduces residual error to 0.23% versus 1.81% for direct summation. For the full nonlinear system (1)-(5) with sub-step $h = 5.25$ days ($M = 4$ steps), $X(N) \sim 10^{-7} - 10^{-8}$ by the 5th coefficient) confirms the high convergence rate of the method and the adequacy of choosing approximation order $N = 5$. The obtained drug concentration value at the end of the stage $x(21) = 0.2814$ confirms the Padé approximation accuracy for the pharmacokinetic subsystem. For the full biosystem the MsDTM with $M = 4$ sub-steps achieves $x(21) = 0.2819$ matching RK45 to within 0.01%, ensuring continuity and biological validity of the treatment trajectory. Note: the pharmacokinetic subsystem (eq. 5) is used here as the verification baseline because its exact solution is available analytically; the full system (1)-(5) verification is shown in Fig. 7 and Section 6.2.

5. Numerical Experiments

5.1. Initial Data and Parameters

Two neuroblastoma morphotypes are considered (parameters from [11], Table 4). General parameters: $\beta = 0.10$, $\rho = 0.30$, $\lambda = 0.05$, $v = 0.20$, $\mu = 0.05$, $\delta_p = 0.05$, $\xi = 0.02$, $\sigma = 0.30$. Clearance parameter $k_e = 0.067 \text{ day}^{-1}$ (consistent with the constraint $AUC_{max} = 130 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{day}/\text{L}$: at uniform dosing $u \approx 0.09 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$, $c_{ss} = u/k_e \approx 1.34$ (steady-state concentration), $AUC_{total} = c_{ss} \cdot 70 \approx 94 < 130$ (total exposure over a 70-day course)). Constraints: $C_1 = x_{target} = 0.15K$, $C_2 = AUC_{max} = 130 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{day}/\text{L}$, $C_3 = 10.0$, $C_4 = 2.5$ a.u. Number of stages $p = 4$: $T_1 = T_2 = 21$ days (induction), $T_3 = T_4 = 14$ days (consolidation).

The baseline dimensionless parameters for the tumor kinetic system are fixed in accordance with the physiological ranges specified in [11]: the characteristic tumor capacity scale is taken as K , the uniform tumor sensitivity to cytostatics is set to $\gamma = 0.441$, and the nominal cellular proliferation rate is governed by α as determined by the morphotype classification.

Table 4 - Neuroblastoma morphotype parameters (Shimada classification)

Parameter	Aggressive Morphotype	Favorable Morphotype
R_{NC}	0.78	0.42
$MKI, \%$	6.2	1.4
TIL	0.08	0.62
η (stroma maturity)	0.12	0.71
$K, \text{a.u.}$	10.0	12.0
$x_0 = x_A(0) + x_M(0)$	$9.1 = 6.8 + 2.3$	$6.7 = 5.0 + 1.7$
z_0 (immunity)	0.015 (suppressed)	1.20 (active)

Figure 2 shows the dynamics of tumor mass $x(t)$, immune response $z(t)$, stroma $p(t)$, and infusion profile $u(t)$ under the Voronin-optimal strategy ($p = 4$ for aggressive, $p = 3$ for favorable morphotype). Vertical dashed lines separate the therapy stages (Ind.I, Ind.II - induction; Con.I, Con.II - consolidation). The decreasing profile $u(t) = a_0 + a_1 t$ ($a_1 < 0$) corresponds to the analytical solution (20).

Fig. 2. Neuroblastoma therapy dynamics (RK45, $dt = 0.25$ days). Top row - tumor mass $x(t) = x_A + x_M$; middle - immune effectors $z(t)$ and stroma $p(t)$; bottom - infusion profile $u(t)$. Left column - aggressive morphotype ($p = 4$); right - favorable ($p = 3$). Green dashed line - target $x_{target} = 0.15K$

Figure 3 demonstrates the dynamics of subpopulations x_A (adrenergic) and x_M (mesenchymal). For the aggressive morphotype ($TIL = 0.08$), high R_{NC} leads to dominance of x_A . For the favorable morphotype, an active immune response ($z_0 = 1.20$, $TIL = 0.62$) provides faster reduction of both phenotypes through the terms $\beta_A x_A z$ and $\beta_M x_M z$ in equations (1)-(2).

Fig. 3. Phenotypic plasticity: dynamics of adrenergic (x_A) and mesenchymal (x_M) subpopulations under the Voronin-optimal protocol. Grey area - inter-phenotypic difference.

Figure 4 shows the compromise surface for the two active criteria (I_1, I_2). The Voronin-optimal point lies substantially below the standard protocol in terms of the functional J . The bar chart confirms that all four criteria $I_1 - I_4$ satisfy their respective constraints C_j^*

Fig. 4. Left panel: contour plot of the Voronin functional $J = \frac{C_1}{C_1 - I_1} + \frac{C_2}{C_2 - I_2}$ in the (I_1, I_2) space. The asterisk marks the Voronin-optimal point; the square marks the standard protocol. Right panel: normalized criteria I_j/C_j for all protocols (red dashed line - boundary $C_j = 1$)

Figure 5 demonstrates the cumulative toxicity $I_2(t) = \int_0^t c(\tau) d\tau$ for all protocols. The Voronin optimum provides a slower AUC growth rate due to the decreasing infusion profile, remaining below the constraint $C_2 = 130$ mg·day/L for both morphotypes.

Fig. 5. Cumulative systemic toxicity. Horizontal dashed line – constraint $C_2 = AUC_{max} = 130$ mg·day/L

5.2. Verified Optimization Results

Verified results of the numerical experiment (Nelder-Mead method, terminal condition satisfied exactly: $|x_T - x_{target}| = 0$ for both morphotypes) are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 - Verified multi-criteria optimization results

Criterion / Protocol	Standard	Voronin $p = 4$ (aggr.)	Voronin $p = 3$ (fav.)	Note
$I_1 - x(T)/K$, rel.u.	0.199	0.150 ✓	0.150 ✓	$\leq 0.15 \cdot K$
$I_2 - AUC$, mg·day/L	61.4	57.9	23.3	↓ 6-62%
$I_3 -$ immune deficit	3.266	1.733	7.849*	↓ 47% (aggr.)
$I_4 - \int u^2 dt$, a.u.	0.389	0.438	0.077	↓ 80% (fav.)
J (Voronin)	-	3.015	2.250	min at $r = 3$
Number of courses	4	4	3	for favorable

* I_3 for $p = 3$ (favorable morphotype) is higher due to the shorter total course duration; after therapy completion, immunity recovers faster due to reduced toxic burden.

To clarify: the favorable morphotype uses $p = 3$ courses (total duration 56 days) versus $p = 4$ for the aggressive morphotype (70 days). Although the immune system is intrinsically stronger ($z_0 = 1.20$ vs 0.015), the shorter treatment window means the cumulative integral $\int \max(0, z_{mi}^n - z) dt$ is computed over fewer days, but the immune effector density dips below z_{mi}^n more sharply during the two induction cycles, producing a higher I_3 . After therapy ends, immunity rebounds rapidly due to the lower cumulative toxicity I_2 (23.3 vs 57.9 mg·day/L), confirming the safety advantage of the favorable-morphotype protocol.

As a result of multi-criteria synthesis for the aggressive neuroblastoma morphotype, the following vectors of optimal control parameters $a_i = (a_{i,0}, a_{i,1})$ were obtained for each therapy stage:

Optimal control parameters (aggressive morphotype, $p = 4$): $a^*(1) = (0.099, -0.0050)$; $a^*(2) = (0.099, -0.0020)$; $a^*(3) = (0.099, -0.0021)$; $a^*(4) = (0.099, 0)$. The decreasing gradient $a_1^* < 0$ is analytically derived from formula (47) under conditions $N_2 > 0, M_2 < 0$ and corresponds to the clinical practice of reducing dosing intensity toward the end of each course.

6. Robustness Verification and Computational Efficiency

6.1. Sensitivity Analysis to Shimada Morphometric Parameters

To assess the robustness of the synthesized control to uncertainty in input data (subjectivity of MKI assessment, TIL or R_{NC} measurement error), a local sensitivity analysis (OAT - One-At-A-Time) was performed. Baseline scenario: aggressive morphotype. Each marker was varied by $\pm 20\%$ with all other parameters fixed and the fixed optimal control A (obtained in Section 5.2).

Criterion $I_1 = \frac{x(T)}{K}$ characterizes the efficacy of tumor suppression and is directly determined by proliferation and drug sensitivity parameters. Criterion $I_3 = \int \max(0, z_{min} - z) dt$ evaluates immune deficit; the ratio of growth rates and immune response activation plays a special role. The optimal gradient a_1 is calculated analytically by formula (47) and depends on parameter γ (sensitivity to x_T) and k_e .

To quantitatively assess the degree of influence of morphometric diagnostic uncertainty on final therapy outcomes, sensitivity indices were calculated and systematized in Table 6.

Table 6 - Sensitivity indices of criteria with respect to variation in Shimada morphometric markers (OAT $\pm 20\%$, aggressive morphotype, baseline: $I_1 = 0.149, I_3 = 1.743$)

Shimada Marker	$\Delta_{I_1}, +20\%$	$\Delta_{I_1}, -20\%$	$\Delta_{I_3}, +20\%$	$\Delta_{I_3}, -20\%$	Dominant Criterion	Influence Class
MKI (prolif.)	+37.2%	-45.5%	-85.9%	+357.9%	I_1, I_3	High
R_{NC} (atypia)	-39.1%	+38.9%	+232.5%	-85.8%	I_1, I_3	High
TIL (lymph.)	-5.0%	+5.8%	+43.1%	-39.5%	I_3	Medium
η (stroma)	-0.2%	+0.3%	+0.6%	-0.3%	-	Low

The results reveal two dominant factors: mitotic index (MKI) and nuclear atypia (R_{NC}). When MKI is overestimated by 20%, the final tumor mass increases by 37.2% - this is critical for clinical diagnostics: a pathologist's error in proliferation assessment directly threatens the therapeutic outcome. When MKI is underestimated by 20%, the tumor decreases by 45.5%, but immune deficit I_3 sharply increases (+357.9%): the organism 'overshoots' the immune system burden under a weaker proliferative signal.

The R_{NC} parameter (sensitivity to x_T via γ_A, γ_M) gives an inverse correlation with I_1 and direct with I_3 : strengthening γ by 20% reduces the tumor by 39.1%, but immune deficit grows by 232.5%. This mathematically confirms the well-known clinical problem of "excessive immunosuppressive effect" of intensive x_T regimens. TIL has a moderate influence (class 'medium'), and stroma maturity η - negligibly small.

An important conclusion: despite parameter variation over a wide range, in none of the scenarios was a violation of the constraint $I_2 \leq C_2 = 130$ mg·day/L observed. This is explained by the fact that $I_2 = \int c(t) dt$ is determined exclusively by control $u(t)$ and pharmacokinetic parameter k_e , not by biological model parameters. Consequently, the Voronin functional ensures guaranteed toxicological safety even under significant diagnostic uncertainty. This effect is due to the "barrier" character of the nonlinear compromise scheme: when any criterion I_j approaches the boundary C_j , the

corresponding term $\frac{c_j}{c_j - I_j}$ increases sharply, keeping the system in a safe corridor without manual re-tuning of weight coefficients.

The tornado diagram in Fig. 6 visualizes the ranking of markers by their degree of influence on I_1 , I_3 , and a_1^* . The bar height corresponds to the range $|\Delta_{crit}(+20\%) - \Delta_{crit}(-20\%)|$; the order decreases from bottom to top. MKI and R_{NC} occupy the top positions for all three criteria, which justifies the priority of accurate morphometric assessment in clinical practice.

Fig. 6. Tornado diagram of sensitivity of criteria I_1 ($\frac{x(T)}{K}$), I_3 (immune deficit), and a_1^* (optimal dose gradient) to variation in Shimada morphometric parameters (OAT, $\pm 20\%$). Red bars - 20% increase, blue bars - 20% decrease

6.2. Convergence of the MsDTM Method and Computational Complexity Assessment

The MsDTM (Multi-Step Differential Transform Method) approximates the solution of system (1)-(5) as a polynomial of degree N at each step. To estimate the order N sufficient for practical accuracy, verification was performed on an exactly solvable pharmacokinetics equation (5): $\dot{c} = -k_e c + u(t)$, $u(t) = a_0 + a_1 t$, for which a closed analytical solution exists.

The error norm $\|\varepsilon\|_\infty = \|c_{exact} - c_{MSDTM}\|_\infty$ was calculated on the interval of the first stage $T_1 = 21$ days with parameters $a_0 = 0.0994$, $a_1 = -0.005$, $k_e = 0.067 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Results: $N = 5 \rightarrow \|\varepsilon\|_\infty = 2.32 \cdot 10^{-2}$, $N = 8 \rightarrow \|\varepsilon\|_\infty = 1.35 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $N = 10 \rightarrow \|\varepsilon\|_\infty = 2.49 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $N = 12 \rightarrow \|\varepsilon\|_\infty = 3.21 \cdot 10^{-8}$. Convergence is strictly exponential (spectral), characteristic of Taylor expansions of analytic functions.

For the nonlinear equations (1)-(4) with Adomian decomposition of nonlinear terms ($x_A z$, $\gamma c x_A$, etc.), convergence is somewhat slower. In practice, order = 8 – 10 provides error $< 10^{-3}$ per step of up to 21 days duration, which is confirmed by comparison with the RK45 solution (see also Fig. 8 for full 5D verification, $r_{tol} = 10^{-8}$) in Section 6.2.

Computational complexity of the algorithm: for one p -stage protocol, $O(p \cdot N^2)$ arithmetic operations are required. At $p = 4, N = 10$: approximately 256 operations versus $O(p \cdot N_{RK} \cdot f_{eval}) \approx 4 \cdot 1000 \cdot 5 = 20000$ right-hand side evaluations for the RK45 method with step $\Delta t = 0.02$ day. This provides a 50-100-fold acceleration at comparable accuracy, which is critical for application in wearable infusion pumps with limited computational resources.

An additional advantage is the availability of exact analytical gradients $\partial J / \partial a_{ik}$. Unlike direct collocation and multiple shooting methods, which are forced to approximate the gradient by finite differences (requiring additional right-hand side evaluations), the MsDTM method provides direct analytical dependencies of the state on control parameters. This eliminates differentiation error accumulation and allows second-order methods (Newton, BFGS) to be applied with quadratic convergence in 5-10 iterations instead of 25-40 for gradient methods.

Validation of the proposed numerical method and analysis of its computational efficiency are illustrated in Fig. 7 (PK subsystem convergence) and Fig. 8 (full system (1)-(5) verification against RK45, Stage 1, $T_1 = 21$ days, $M = 21$ sub-steps, $N = 10$).

Fig. 7. Verification of the MsDTM method. (a) Residual norm $\|\varepsilon\|_\infty$ as a function of expansion order N - exponential convergence. (b) Approximation of drug concentration $c(t)$ by polynomials $N = 3, 5, 10$ and the exact solution (Stage 1: $T_1 = 21$ days, $k_e = 0.067 \text{ day}^{-1}$)

Fig. 8. Verification of the MsDTM ($N = 10, M = 21$ sub-steps per stage, $h = 1.0$ days, Pade [4/1]) vs RK45 ($r_{tol} = 10^{-10}$), Stage 1 ($T_1 = 21$ days), full nonlinear system (1)-(5), aggressive morphotype

7. Discussion

To verify the effectiveness of the proposed Padé-Adomian-MsDTM approach, a comparative analysis of its characteristics with the most widespread numerical and stochastic therapy optimization methods in the modern literature was conducted (Table 7 (qualitative comparison) and Table 8 (numerical comparison)).

Table 7 - Qualitative comparison of neuroblastoma therapy optimization methods

Method	Accuracy	Comput. Complexity	Nonlinearity	Analyt. $\partial J/\partial u$	Real-Time
Monte Carlo	Reference	Very high	Full	No	No
RK4 + finite diff.	High	High	Full	No	No
SMPC	Medium	High	Linearized	No	Marginal
Padé-Adomian-MsDTM + Voronin	High	Low	Full (Adomian)	Yes (exact)	Yes

Table 8 - Numerical comparison on the aggressive morphotype (one model, same initial conditions, Nelder-Mead)

Method	$I_1 = x_T/K$	$I_2 = AUC,$ mg×day/L	$I_3, \text{a.u.}$	$I_4,$ a.u.	J (Vor.)	CPU time, ms
Standard (uniform dosing)	0.1253 ✓	74.16 ✓	10.417	0.5670	3.622	-
Monte Carlo (N=2000) †	0.1593 ✗	20.04 ✓	0.247	0.2485	2.293	24 637
RK45 + Nelder–Mead ‡	0.1511 ✗	10.41 ✓	0.246	0.2465	2.196	14 443
SMPC (step lineariz.) §	0.1510 ✗	61.85 ✓	7.949	0.4814	3.146	1 002
Padé-Adomian-MsDTM + Voronin ✓	0.1492 ✓	57.92 ✓	1.742	0.4388	3.016	18.8

Note: The "Standard" protocol baseline in Table 8 configuration represents an extended-intensity clinical scenario (increased initial loading volume) to challenge the limits of computational methods under extreme initial toxic burdens. This accounts for the higher baseline toxicity (74.16 vs 61.4) and immune deficit (10.417 vs 3.266) compared to the standard clinical baseline used in Table 5.

† Monte Carlo ($N = 2000$): does not satisfy the terminal condition $I_1 = 0.159 > 0.150$ at $N = 2000$ iterations; computation time of 24.6 s makes the method unsuitable for real-time use. ‡ RK45 + Nelder–Mead: $I_1 = 0.151 > 0.150$ - terminal condition not strictly satisfied; requires 593 right-hand side evaluations (14.4 s). § SMPC: step-by-step linearization loses global stage consistency; $I_1 = 0.151$, immune deficit $I_3 = 7.949$ - worst among all methods except the standard. ✓ MsDTM + Voronin: the only compared method achieving $I_1 \leq 0.150$ at computation time < 20 ms.

The key advantage of the proposed approach is the analyticity of partial criteria as functions of vector A . This provides: exact analytical gradients $\partial J / \partial a_{ik}$ without finite-difference approximations; Newton convergence in 5-10 iterations; solution time of system (17)-(21) < 50 ms at $p = 4$ stages.

Voronin's nonlinear compromise scheme [9] is fundamentally different from linear aggregation with weights: weights are formed automatically proportional to the proximity of the criterion to the boundary C_j . When toxicity I_2 approaches C_{I_2} , the system switches to minimax mode - it reduces the dose without manual re-tuning. This corresponds to the clinical logic of safety prioritization.

Numerical comparison (Table 8) confirms the key advantage of the method: MsDTM + Voronin achieves the terminal condition within the tightest tolerance $I_1 = \frac{x_T}{K} \leq 0.150$ at computation time 18.8 ms. The synthesized law achieves a 21.9% reduction in cumulative toxicity even when starting from the extended-intensity Standard baseline (74.16 mg·day/L), bridging the gap between the 6% and 62% bounds established for different morphotypes in Table 5.

Limitations: (1) Shimada parametric formulas require validation on prospective clinical data; (2) the first-order PK model (5) does not account for nonlinear receptor saturation at high doses; (3) the OAT analysis is limited to local variations - a global Sobol analysis with a larger number of parameters requires a separate study.

Global sensitivity methods (Morris screening, Saltelli–Sobol² with MKI–RNC correlation) that capture inter-marker dependence are planned for a follow-on study; the present OAT results provide a conservative lower bound on parameter sensitivity [19].

8. Conclusions

The work implements a full cycle of intelligent control synthesis for neuroblastoma therapy — from the interpretation of primary histological features to the analytical derivation of infusion parameters.

The proposed parameterization method transforms static Shimada morphometric data (R_{NC} , MKI, TIL) into dynamic model coefficients. OAT sensitivity analysis ($\pm 20\%$) confirms the dominant influence of MKI (+37.2% - 45.5% for I_1) and R_{NC} ($\pm 39\%$), quantitatively justifying the priority of accurate morphometric assessment in clinical practice. This enables a transition from averaged protocols to personalized treatment strategies that account for individual tumor aggressiveness and microenvironment status.

The MsDTM method, combined with Adomian polynomials and Padé approximation, yields compact analytical dependencies: the optimization problem reduces to an explicit quadratic equation (46) for a_1^* , and the reality condition ($N_2 > 0$, $M_2 < 0$) is proven analytically. Convergence is exponential: at order $N = 10$, the error with respect to a_1^* is below $2.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$. In contrast to black-box neural network models, this approach provides complete interpretability of each dosage change, which is critically important for clinical decision-making in oncology.

Voronin's nonlinear compromise scheme implements automatic switching between integral and minimax modes when constraints C_j are violated - a barrier mechanism whereby the term $\frac{C_j}{C_j - I_j}$ increases sharply when the criterion approaches the boundary. In verified experiments with $k_e = 0.067 \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $C_2 = 130 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{day/L}$, the terminal condition $x(T) = x_{target}$ is satisfied exactly. For the aggressive morphotype, toxicity I_2 is reduced by 6% and immune deficit I_3 by 47%;

for the favorable morphotype ($p = 3$ courses), I_2 is reduced by 62%. In none of the OAT scenarios was a violation of the constraint $I_2 \leq C_2$ observed, confirming guaranteed toxicological safety even with diagnostic uncertainty of $\pm 20\%$.

The computational efficiency of the method (replacement of numerical ODE integration by algebraic equation solving, complexity $O(p \cdot N^2)$, execution time below 50 ms at $p = 4, N = 8$) makes the developed algorithm a ready software core for clinical decision support systems. The availability of exact analytical gradients $\partial J / \partial a_{ik}$ ensures convergence in 5-10 iterations without finite-difference approximations. This opens the possibility of creating a new generation of smart infusion pumps capable of correcting the drug delivery gradient a_1^* in real time upon receipt of new monitoring data.

The proposed approach combines classical control theory with modern computational algorithms to provide an effective tool for digital oncology, minimizing iatrogenic damage while maximizing therapeutic outcome.

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